

Thermal properties of 1,1'-bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexanes

K. M. Rajkotia and P. H. Parsania*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005, India

Manuscript received 30 July 1997, revised 24 June 1998, accepted 20 July 1998

DSC thermograms of 1,1'-bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexanes 3, 8, 14 and 15 showed two endotherms whereas 2, 4-7, 9, 11-13, 16 and 17 showed more than two endotherms indicating formation of new compounds as a result of decomposition of original compound. TG thermograms of 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 11-13 and 15 involved a single step decomposition whereas 3, 6, 7, 9, 10, 14, 16 and 17 involved two step degradation and involved first order kinetics.

Various bisphenols have been found to possess biological activities but most of them are toxic to the host cells. This problem can be overcome by easily hydrolysable ester derivatives. The literature survey on bisphenol esters¹ reveals scanty work in this field. With a view to assess usefulness of these type of compounds, present work explores thermal properties of 1,1'-bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexanes (1).

Results and Discussion

Several methods² have been proposed for estimation of kinetic parameters. All these methods involve two important assumptions that thermal and diffusion barriers are negligible and Arrhenius equation is valid. DSC methods³ especially Ozawa⁴ and Kissinger⁵ methods based on the variable programme rate have been successfully used for the industrial materials and kinetic parameters can be derived from the peak temperature programme rate relationships.

Fig. 1 shows typical DSC thermograms of compounds 2

and 3. The transition temperatures and heat of reactions (ΔH) for 1-17 are reported in Table 1. The endotherm(s) is/are due to melting transition(s) of original or new compounds formed as a result of decomposition of original compound and the exotherms are due to crystallization of the compounds. Two (3, 8, 14 and 15) or more than two (2, 4-7, 9, 11-13, 16 and 17) endothermic transitions support

Fig. 1. DSC thermograms of 2 and 3 at 10⁰/min in an N₂ atmosphere. the formation of new compounds as a result of decomposition of original compound and because of this reason other kinetic parameters have not been evaluated.

Table 1. Transition temperatures and heat of reactions (ΔH) derived from DSC data of compounds 1-17

Compd. no.	Transition	Trans. temp., K	ΔH Jg ⁻¹
1	Endo	415.85	19.6
	Exo	525.55	-106.7
2	Exo	642.55	-399.3
	Exo	642.55	-399.3
3	Endo	358.65	15.9
	Endo	453.75	131.5
	Endo	624.95	413.4
	Exo	686.15	-124.5
4	Endo	455.85	156.8
	Endo	662.05	158.0
5	Endo	363.65	40.1
	Endo	420.05	56.4
6	Endo	645.35	380.6
	Endo	367.35	144.4
	Endo	441.05	15.4
	Endo	451.75	15.9
	Endo	458.35	22.4
7	Endo	633.85	292.1
	Endo	346.65	14.2
	Endo	435.55	50.5
8	Endo	448.55	45.1
	Exo	615.85	-332.4
	Endo	350.05	81.0
	Endo	443.15	49.1
9	Endo	471.35	3.9
	Endo	610.05	455.1
	Endo	714.25	4.0
	Endo	441.05	14.5
	Endo	549.35	105.3
10	Endo	382.55	32.4
	Endo	425.85	17.6
	Endo	454.05	4.6
11	Endo	488.65	79.0
	Exo	595.05	-412.2
12	Endo	652.55	-236.3
	Endo	343.15	-
13	Endo	406.45	-
	Endo	616.15	-
	Exo	648.15	-
	Endo	322.45	5.7
14	Endo	417.85	18.0
	Endo	452.45	82.2
	Endo	667.05	160.6
	Endo	712.75	3.6
	Endo	780.95	25.6
15	Endo	415.65	3.3
	Endo	461.15	70.5
	Exo	671.65	-302.1
16	Endo	439.85	47.3
	Endo	487.55	68.2
	Endo	368.85	75.9
	Exo	404.95	29.4
17	Endo	509.15	-544.5
	Endo	372.35	44.8
	Endo	432.95	42.9
	Endo	463.35	8.3
	Endo	573.85	23.6
17	Endo	597.65	24.9
	Endo	374.85	28.0
	Endo	449.95	86.4
	Endo	475.65	6.0
17	Endo	635.15	325.1
	Endo	677.65	106.9

Fig. 3. TG thermograms of 3, 6, 7, 9, 10, 14, 16 and 17 at 10^o/min in an N₂ atmosphere.

Figs. 2 and 3 show TG thermograms of 1-17. It is evident that compounds 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 11-13 and 15 involved a single step degradation whereas 3, 6, 7, 9, 10, 14, 16 and 17 involved two step degradation. Initial decomposition temperature, decomposition temperature range, % weight-loss and temperature of maximum degradation are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Initial decomposition temperature (IDT), decomposition range and temperature of maximum degradation for compounds 1-17

Compd. no.	IDT K	Decomp. range	Weight-loss %	Temp. of max. degrad. K
1	529.5	529-621	91.0	591
2	618.2	618-651	82.0	644
3	387.0	387-451	30.5	434
	525.7	526-638	52.0	562
4	535.7	536-651	90.5	581
5	540.7	541-586	80.0	573
6	424.2	424-463	30.0	446
	538.2	538-581	46.0	561
7	449.2	449-477	55.0	470
8	513.2	513-566	30.0	553
	435.7	436-574	81.5	554
9	465.7	466-498	55.0	489

Table-2 (contd.)

10	498.2	498-558	28.0	534
	530.7	531-703	63.0	614
	798.2	798-836	10.0	823
11	493.2	493-521	64.0	500
12	453.2	453-506	72.5	490
13	553.2	553-608	84.5	596
14	408.2	408-448	35.5	442
	485.7	486-553	42.5	507
15	523.2	523-556	79.0	546
16	435.7	436-498	21.5	466
	573.2	603-666	28.0	610
17	433.2	433-467	45.0	458
	467.0	467-538	25.0	503

The energy of activation (E_a) for compounds 1-17 was determined according to methods of single heating rate of Horowitz-Metzger², and first order equation, $\ln(1-C) = E_a/RT + \ln AR/\beta E_a$, where C is the degree fractional change. The least-square values of E_a and correlation coefficient (γ) for 1-17 are reported in Table 3. The observed correlation coefficient is good to excellent and on the basis it is presumed that compounds 1-17 followed first order kinetics.

Table 3. Energy of activation (E_a) and correlation coefficient (γ) for compounds 1-17

Compd. no.	E_a , kJ mol ⁻¹		γ	
	H-M eqn.	First order eqn.	H-M eqn.	First order eqn.
1	71.9	121.7	0.9534	0.9999
2	278.6	108.2	0.9924	0.9865
3	37.4	54.3	0.9936	0.9835
	32.4	46.1	0.9829	0.9988
4	72.7	153.5	0.9968	0.9921
	59.4	72.6	0.9979	0.9882
5	108.6	112.9	1.0001	0.9958
6	76.6	65.9	0.9998	0.9801
7	101.2	62.6	0.9971	0.9982
	49.2	43.9	0.9806	0.9809
8	72.0	112.9	0.9964	0.9978
9	96.7	121.8	0.9921	0.9998
	72.7	63.5	0.9963	0.9687
10	62.2	95.7	0.9828	0.9963
	30.1	110.6	0.9913	0.9955
11	90.7	63.2	0.9953	0.9996
12	86.0	76.2	0.9779	0.9984
13	127.5	147.1	0.9575	0.9521
14	60.6	57.8	0.9983	0.9985
	37.0	42.1	0.9858	0.9923
15	152.1	173.6	0.9575	0.9979
16	31.1	50.16	0.9963	0.9998
	23.9	33.44	0.9992	0.9994
17	86.9	77.6	0.9971	0.9968
	23.0	40.1	0.9803	0.9967

Scheme 1

From DSC data, it is found that degradation process is complex involving a variety of reactions such as cleavage, rearrangement, decomposition and so on. The ester linkage and side-substituents are the weak points in the ester molecule and they degrade selectively (Scheme 1). The calculated and observed weight-loss as a result of decomposition is found to be approximately the same. The radicals formed as a result of decomposition of ester linkage or side-substituent may combine to form new product(s) which further degrade at elevated temperature to yield low molecular mass hydrocarbons besides CO_2 and side-substituent product(s).

Experimental

1,1'-Bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)-cyclohexanes were synthesised from substituted bisphenols and benzoyl chlorides using 1,4-dioxane as a solvent and pyridine as a catalyst. All the compounds were purified repeatedly from water-methanol system⁵ prior to use.

DSC and TG thermograms were scanned in N_2 atmosphere using Mettler DSC and Perkin-Elmer TGA instruments respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. R. Parikh for encouragement.

References

1. "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", eds. I. M. Kolthoff, P. J. Elving and F. H. Stross, Wiley, New York, 1976, Part III, Vol. 3; P. B. Marsh, M. L. Butler and B. S. Clark, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, **41**, 2176; C. H. Arndt, *Phytopathology*, 1948, **38**, 978; A. M. Islam, E. A. Hasan, M. E. Rashid and M. M. Wassel, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1980, **20**, 483; C. A. Wilson, US Pat. 4457922/1984; G. Subramaniam, R. Savithri and S. Thambipillai, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 797.

Rajkotia *et al.* : Thermal properties of 1,1'-bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexanes

2. E. S. Freeman and B. Carroll, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 394; A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 68; T. Ozawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **38**, 1881; W. W. Wendlandt "Thermal Methods of Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1974; H. H. Horowitz and Metzger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464; J. H. Flynn and L. A. Wall, *Polym. Lett.*, 1966, **4**, 323; P. Kofstad, *Nature*, 1957, **179**, 1362.
3. H. E. Kissinger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1702; P. Murray and J. White, *Trans. Br. Ceram. Soc.*, 1955, **54**, 204; F. Vaughan, *Clayminerals Bull.*, 1955, **2**, 265; H. J. Borchardt and F. J. Daniels, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 41; W. W. Wendlandt, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1961, **38**, 571.
4. T. Ozawa, *J. Ther. Anal.*, 1970, **2**, 301.
5. K. M. Rajkotia and P. H. Parsania, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 524.